

MONETARY POLICY AND THE EXCHANGE RATE REGIME IN UKRAINE SINCE 2014

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Since the beginning of 2013, Ukraine has experienced a range of social, political, and economic shocks, including revolution, change of political elite, loss of part of the territory, military conflict, the epidemic of Covid-19, and all the supporting economic consequences. The country has entered a period of a deep economic and financial crisis, which has been supported by the financial system's volatility and imbalances in the external area. The result has been the devaluation of a national currency, which has a crucial impact on the main macroeconomic indicators. A choice of an exchange rate regime in a small open national economy has a defining impact on the mentioned indicators and macroeconomic equilibrium, in general. Since 2015, the National Bank of Ukraine (the NBU) has declared a transition to the policy of inflation targeting in the conditions of the floating exchange rate regime. Nonetheless, the practice has shown that the regulator partially follows the stated policy, influencing the exchange rate via currency interventions. Adjustment of fluctuations of the exchange rate is often performed for political and business purposes, lowering the degree of flexibility of the exchange rate and moving against the existing market conditions, which causes significant losses for economic agents, in particular, and a whole national economy, in general. Individuals and businesses have high devaluation expectations in Ukraine. They are more sensitive and vulnerable to the oscillations of the exchange rate. Monetary policy, which does not meet market realities in the conditions of the floating exchange rate regime, exposes economic signals for businesses and individuals and does not lead to the realization of the stated goals.

Crisis phenomena and disproportions are present in all the areas of a national economy of Ukraine, which seriously complicates a choice of the most optimal economic policy, including a monetary one. Severe conditions of the country's economy can be traced via the main macroeconomic indicators from such areas as production, employment, external area, and area of prices. The main economic indicators of Ukraine's national economy for 2013-2019 are presented in table 1 below [1].

Table 1
The main macroeconomic indicators of Ukraine for 2013-2019

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	-0.2	12.1	48.7	13.9	14.4	11.0	7.9
Current account balance (% of GDP)	-9.0	-3.4	5.5	-2.0	-3.1	-4.9	-2.7

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Unemployment, total (% of total labor force)	7.2	9.3	9.1	9.4	9.5	8.8	8.9
GDP growth (annual %)	0.0	-6.6	-9.8	2.2	2.5	3.4	3.2

The principal macroeconomics problems of Ukraine in the last years have been the following: stable high rates of inflation and unemployment, a negative balance of the current account, and insufficient GDP growth rates. The average pace of inflation (consumer price index - CPI) has been 15.40% for the analyzed seven years, reaching the peak in 2015, when the military conflict in Eastern Ukraine was in the hot phase. The trend to the decline of inflation rate has been monitored after 2015, which may be evidence of the central bank policy's efficiency and improvement of macroeconomic conditions in the country. According to the NBU, CPI was only 5.00% in 2020, achieving a sated midterm goal of monetary policy [2]. Despite this fact, a national economy remains in crisis conditions, in general.

There are a lot of discussions in academic and professional fields on whether such a pace of inflation is beneficial for the country's economy. Ukraine experienced a severe economic recession during 2013-2015, losing 16.40% of GDP. The existing economic growth rates are not sufficient to guarantee a proper level of life of the country's citizens. Lower inflation rates do not lead to the reduction of unemployment and do not boost economic growth, which makes the inflation target of NBU a quite isolated goal, which is independent of other economic realities. For instance, it does not solve the problem of stable high unemployment (1,798,146.00 million people), low productivity, and growth rates. The local citizens earn revenues in a national currency, and devaluation of hryvnia causes loss of assets for them. The current economic situation in Ukraine requires a more stimulating policy. Choice of character, instruments, and direction of monetary policy is not an easy task, since it is necessary to maintain a balance between growth, price stability, and stability of a national currency.

Restrictive monetary policy was conducted in the worst period of the economic crisis, including maintaining a high key policy rate. A key policy rate was chosen as the main instrument of monetary policy. The main task was to cut the inflation rates, and the regulator has managed to achieve this goal since 2016. NBU has chosen to reduce a key policy rate in recent years (2018-2020) to stimulate a national economy since the average unemployment rate in the last years has been 8.88%, and the average GDP growth rate has been - - 0.73%. A key policy rate and its correlation with the exchange rate and inflation are presented in table 2.

Table 2

A key policy rate, the exchange rate and pace of inflation in Ukraine

Year	Key policy rate	Exchange rate	Inflation
2013	6,50%	7,99	-0,20%
2014	14,00%	15,62	12,10%

Year	Key policy rate	Exchange rate	Inflation
2015	22,00%	23,41	48,70%
2016	14,00%	26,2	13,90%
2017	14,50%	27,52	14,40%
2018	18,00%	27,79	11,00%
2019	13,50%	23,61	7,90%
2020	6,00%	28,27	5,00%

A key policy rate has been mainly used to react to the changes in the level of prices. There has been not a vivid correlation between a key policy rate and the exchange rate's movement. The NBU has been using other instruments to influence the level of the exchange rate, including currency interventions. According to the NBU, currency interventions are made mainly to adjust abrupt fluctuations on the market and to fill the international reserves. The dynamics of a key policy rate, CPI, and the exchange rate are presented on figure 1.

Figure 1. The dynamics of a key policy rate, exchange rate and CPI in Ukraine

The essence of the inflation targeting policy is a public announcement by the NBU of the desired inflation rate and the obligation to reach it within a stated midterm period. According to the basic principles of the monetary policy of the NBU, the current midterm inflation goal is 5.00% with possible fluctuations within +/- 1.00%. Therefore, the target was reached last year. The question is whether it is better for a national economy. The National Bank of Ukraine increased a key policy rate for the purpose of keeping inflation during the worst period of the crisis. The rate reached the level of 30.00% during 2015. Alongside with decline in industrial production, a policy of expensive money has led to downturn of GDP and a growth of unemployment. After cutting the inflation, the NBU moved on to stimulating monetary policy, declining a key policy rate to the level of 6.00% in 2020 [3]. The goal is to make financial resources cheaper and more available for businesses and individuals. The efficiency of this policy is going to show itself in some period. However, it is also important to account the exchange rate. A lot of commercial credits are approved in foreign currency, a lot of businesses are oriented on foreign markets, and the share of imported goods and services is quite high in national commodity circulation. That is why devaluation of a national currency may be harmful to the internal economic agents. Even the presence of cheap money does not force individuals and businesses to make long-term decisions,

borrow money, increase investments and consumption in the conditions of the devaluation of a national currency and high devaluation expectations. Leaving the exchange rate outside the scope of monetary policy does not allow this policy to achieve the stated objectives.

The dynamics of the exchange rate of hryvnia for the last seven years are presented on figure 2. As it can be seen, a trend towards the devaluation of a national currency has been present. Hryvnia has devaluated almost three times related to USD for those years. The greatest decline was present in 2014, and the first quarter of 2015. It was caused by the mentioned social, economic and political factors.

Figure 2. Dynamics of the exchange rate of Hryvnia

The second reason for the devaluation was the fact that the NBU has shifted to the floating exchange rate regime, and the formation of the hryvnia's exchange rate has been delegated to the market forces. Devaluation of hryvnia has been smoother after that transition. Market forces can balance tremendous fluctuations of supply and demand for national currency and make it closer to equilibrium. According to the principles of the floating exchange rate regime, the NBU has not used any monetary instruments to establish a certain level or range of the exchange rate. The floating exchange rate regime allows minimum interference of central bank into currency market's performance in the form of currency interventions to eliminate severe fluctuations of the exchange rate, but not establishing its level. Since 2015 currency interventions have been targeted also on the accumulation of the international reserves [4]. It is essential to analyze the dynamics of the international reserves, which are presented on figure 3.

Figure 3. International reserves in Ukraine, million USD

Following own statement of the NBU, growth of the international reserves has been possible thanks to the beneficial situation on the internal currency market – a surplus of supply of foreign currency over demand for it, which has been bought by NBU via the mechanism of interventions (net purchase of foreign currency by NBU has been \$7.9 billion for 2019, what has been the greatest value for the last 14 years). The dynamics of currency interventions of NBU for the last seven years are presented on figure 4.

Figure 4. Currency interventions by NBU (net purchase)

As it can be seen, the NBU has mainly purchased foreign currency for recent years (2016-2020). Therefore, a supply of foreign currency has exceeded the demand for it. In such conditions, the exchange rate of a national currency had to become stronger, which had not happened actually. The NBU has bought foreign currency and brought a redundant volume of hryvnia to market. It has not allowed the exchange rate of hryvnia to appreciate or even led to devaluation. Thus, it is possible to talk about the managed floating exchange rate regime in Ukraine. Managed floating exchange rate regime provides the central bank's intentions to influence the exchange rate level without clearly established levels or ranges. As a rule, signals to interfere are the following: conditions of the balance of payments, international reserves, etc [5]. The main disadvantage of the managed floating exchange rate regime is the fact that the regulator can manipulate the exchange rate to benefit specific industries or economic classes. Especially it is intrinsic to the countries with a high degree of political and economic corruption, to which Ukraine belongs. The most powerful country's

exporters or importers may lobby beneficial for them directions of the exchange rate policies. Very often the NBU becomes a hostage of political situations and political promises, which does not correspond with the statement about total independence of the regulator.

In conclusion, Ukraine has faced a range of serious economic and political crises in recent years. The situation has required adequate economic policy, which would stimulate the growth of a national economy, on the one hand, and would not allow critical inflation and devaluation of a national currency. Since Ukraine is a country with a small open economy, such indicators as balance of payments, current account, and exchange rate are critical for it. The National Bank of Ukraine declared a transition to inflation targeting and the floating exchange rate regime in 2015. In practice, it meant refusal to maintain a fixed exchange rate, which had not reflected economic realities, and concentration of the regulator's efforts on maintenance of the stated level of prices. Accounting a high share of imports in the country's GDP, caused by the change of the exchange rate regime devaluation has combined with a high pace of inflation and forced NBU to conduct restrictive monetary policy, increasing a key policy rate. Currently, a key policy rate is lowered to minimal levels to stimulate a national economy, but it does not affect the currency's exchange rate. NBU performs regular currency interventions, mainly purchasing foreign currency and keeping hryvnia from appreciation. Such steps do not take into account devaluation expectations of the individuals and businesses. As a result, efficiency of the monetary policy is lowered, and stable economic growth is not achieved.

References:

1. The World Bank. (n.d.). *World Development Indicators*. Retrieved from <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>
2. The National Bank of Ukraine. (n.d.). *The National Bank of Ukraine Annual Report 2019*. Retrieved from https://bank.gov.ua/admin_uploads/article/annual_report_2019_final-eng.pdf?v=4
3. *The National Bank of Ukraine Official Website*. Retrieved from <https://bank.gov.ua/>
4. Grui, A. (2020). *Uncovered interest parity with foreign exchange interventions under exchange rate peg and inflation targeting: The case of Ukraine* (No. 14-2020). Economics Section, The Graduate Institute of International Studies.
5. IMF. (n.d.). *Classification of Exchange Rate Arrangements and Monetary Policy Frameworks*. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/external/np/mfd/er/2003/eng/0603.htm>